

PERSPECTIVE DEVELOPMENTS OF INTERACTIVE LEARNING METHODS

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Annotation. The article discusses the use of interactive methods in education. The relevance and development of the methodology of mutual learning, as well as methods of group work of students, are being studied. The criteria for selecting interactive teaching methods, the main activities of the teacher are analyzed.

Keywords. Interactive methods, teaching, pedagogical problems, free grouping, etc.

Introduction

Learning and development are perennial pedagogical problems. At different stages of human society, even in different ethnic communities, social groups, this problem was periodically updated, they tried to solve it and solved it in different ways. The goal of personal development has forced Russian education to revisit the problem of learning and development, seeking to find the most correct solution to it. However, teachers at all levels of the education system, who are more or less involved in solving this problem, as options for overcoming it arise, exponentially, new questions appear without specific answers. With the undoubted merits of other developmental methods, we will pay attention to interactive teaching methods, which are based on the cognitive joint activity of the teacher and students. At the same time, it is important to recall that in the context of the organization of educational work, in particular interactive interaction, the form of planning and organization of training determines the choice of the leading method.

It should be recognized that today it is impossible to achieve the goal, solve the problems of teaching schoolchildren without creating conditions for independent appropriation, acquisition and comprehension of knowledge by them.

The task of a modern teacher at present is not to present knowledge to schoolchildren, but more practical and pragmatic - to create motivation and form a set of universal general educational skills and actions in order to teach oneself. It is obvious that any skill does not come to the student without the help of a teacher. Cooperation between a teacher and a student presupposes the knowledge and ability of the teacher to dose and direct the independence provided to the student, which ultimately leads to goal-setting, designing his educational activities as the basis of personal formation and development.

In the learning process, the most qualitative perception and assimilation of educational material occurs as a result of interpersonal cognitive communication and interaction of all subjects. Methods of group interaction are usually called interactive. They are based on the process of game interaction, or the mechanism of interaction.

Interaction is understood as direct interpersonal communication, intercourse. The most important feature of interaction is the ability of a person to accept and understand the role of another; imagine how a communication partner or a group perceives him and, in accordance with this, plan his own actions.

Methods

The purpose of interactive learning for a modern school in the context of its modernization is considered the overall development of schoolchildren, providing each of them with optimal opportunities in personal formation and development, in expanding the possibilities of self-determination and self-realization. At the same time, the general development of the student includes the development of personality neoplasms in his/her needs, intellectual, emotional and volitional spheres.

The result of such communication is the creation of didactic conditions for students to experience the situation of success in the process of learning activities and mutual enrichment of their motivational, intellectual and other areas. It is assumed that cooperation, interaction, activity of the teacher and students in a

relatively short period of time ensures the formation and development of operational, above-subject, universal skills and actions that determine the success of a particular activity of the student. In other words, interactive learning is more efficient and effective than teaching each student individually in this direction. What is especially important, negative personal acquisitions of a student can be corrected, changed in the process of interactive learning, although students independently correct their knowledge and ability to use it rationally [6].

Research

Interactive learning as a form of cognitive activity has very specific goals, aimed primarily at creating comfortable conditions for educational work, which provides the student with independence, initiative and productivity of his cognitive activity. At the same time, all students - partners, cooperating (exchanging opinions, judgments, ideas, ways of activity), make their individual contribution to the common cause (task completion).

Interaction to acquire new knowledge and methods of activity raises the cognitive and social experience of students to a new, higher level of development, forms cooperation and cooperation. Interaction does not allow the predominance of one of the partners, one opinion over the other. It presupposes equality, benevolence and activity of all in mutual cognitive activity. In interactive learning, the partner begins to be recognized as a value, because thanks to this person, another person develops. This is especially active in the process of discussion, opposition, which encourages the applicant to delve deeper, to see the other side of the issue under discussion. This is precisely what distinguishes the interactive learning that is currently in demand in all education systems of developed countries. In the process of interactive learning, pair and group work is organized in the classroom, during which documents and various sources of information are studied, conditions are created for research and other

Within the framework of interactive learning, various methods and technologies are used as ways of organizing learning activities. The task of developing schoolchildren, which is successfully carried out in the process of interactive learning, is realized through the organization of students' activities, built taking into account the laws of the psyche of children of a particular age (which is one of the principles of developmental education).

The most common group form of education. In the middle of the 20th century, K. Levin put forward the idea: "it is usually easier to change individuals gathered in a group than to change any of them individually." This is a special difference between interactive learning: learning takes place in group joint activities, including through mutual learning. At the same time, when organizing interactive learning, it is important to take into account that along with the solution of educational goals and objectives, in the process of group interactions, the value of other children was realized and the need to communicate with them and support them was formed.

The group form of training allows you to simultaneously solve three problems:

- a certain cognitive task arising from a specific learning situation;
- communicative-developing, during which conditions are created and communication skills are formed both inside and outside the given group;
- social orientation, forming and developing civic qualities necessary for adequate socialization of the student in modern society.

Based on this, the most acceptable, simple and effective way to organize interactive learning is to work in groups (small and large). As a rule, group work allows:

- in a short time to study and discuss a voluminous and sometimes contradictory block of material for comprehension and understanding;
- solve the problems of differentiated and multi-level learning within the lesson;
- productively form general educational skills and educational activities that they implement;

- optimize and activate the processes of socialization of schoolchildren.

The tasks that are offered for study, discussion by students must certainly be of a problematic, research, developmental and creative nature of different levels of difficulty and complexity. Reproductive (for reproduction) questions are ineffective in this case.

Interactive methods are understood as a system of rules and characteristic features of interaction between a teacher and students in the form of educational games and situations that provide pedagogically effective cognitive communication.

Until recently, the concept of "interactive dialogue" referred mainly to the work, the description of information systems. Today, this phrase has already become quite firmly established in pedagogical science. As is often the case in pedagogy, this form and/or method of teaching has a long history. It originates at the end of the 18th century, first in India, then in Great Britain, and then in other countries, including Russia. This method was proposed independently by English teachers E. Bell and J. Lancaster. After their name, the method was subsequently called the Bell-Lancaster system of mutual learning and became widespread as a quick and cheap way of learning in the conditions of the development of capitalist production, which needed a significant number of educated people. Group forms of training workers gave a quick, expected result.

The return of relevance and development of the methodology of mutual learning occurred at the beginning of the 20th century, when E. Parkhest proposed the Dalton Plan. Russia has its own analogue - the brigade-laboratory method. Another wave of interest in this method, as new to our time, was caused by the development of the humanistic trend in foreign psychology. The result of the revision of the ideas of A. Maslow and K. Rogers was the domestic pedagogy of cooperation, which sharply set the task for teachers and psychologists to change the content and structure of traditional pedagogical interactions. At that time, the

concept of collaborative pedagogy was not developed into technology, but at present this experience is being intensively developed.

Interactive methods include educational business games, brainstorming, role-playing, game design, analysis of specific problem (or other) situations, and others. In the process of interactive communication in pairs, groups (small and large), between groups, students develop knowledge, including their own opinion, on a particular event, phenomenon, active life position, creative abilities; speech, a sense of responsibility for a common cause develop, ideas, concepts are systematized, analyzed, concretized and corrected; logical connections are established that contribute to the understanding of the patterns of social life in all its diversity, etc. The systematic use by the teacher of interactive methods in the classroom creates favorable conditions for mastering different social attitudes, roles and functions, mastering learning activities.

Criteria for selection of interactive teaching methods:

- compliance with the goals and objectives of training and development of schoolchildren;
- compliance with the didactic objectives of the lesson;
- compliance with the content of the topic of the lesson;
- compliance with the age, intellectual capabilities of schoolchildren and the level of their education and upbringing, the characteristics of the class as a whole;
- compliance with the time frame of training;
- compliance with the professionalism and experience of a particular teacher;
- compliance with the method of managing educational activities;
- compliance with the logic of the educational process.

The basis of the teacher's activity in the conditions of interactive learning is a student-centered approach. The main requirements for observing a person-centered approach:

- humane pedagogical position of the teacher;

- value attitude to the student, creativity;
- creation of cultural-informational and subject-developing environment;
- possession of methodology and basics of educational technology;
- focus on the development of the student's individuality [3].

In the process of organizing, managing and controlling the development of interactive communication between schoolchildren, the teacher mainly uses indirect methods of pedagogical activity, giving students independence in choosing the means to achieve the goal, adequate learning actions, and partners in activities.

When working in the mode of interactive learning, it is important to prevent didactic monotony, isolation of communication within groups. The main principle of interactive learning is the organization of an intensive dialogue within the groups, which, if necessary, is replaced by a polylogue. Dialogue takes place within groups, and as a result of communication between groups, a polylogue arises. With a combination of pedagogical and psychological conditions, interactive learning as a form of the educational process is able to optimize the essence, content and structure of pedagogical interactions.

By its design, interactive learning can be a method or technology, depending on the way the educational work of the teacher and students is organized in solving certain didactic problems. In any case, this type of training is designed to solve communication-developing and socially-oriented tasks.

Interactive learning also includes user-computer interaction. All types of training and game programs, Internet resources are the content for this type of activity. However, it should be understood that interaction with technical means is communication (one-way communication), and communication (two-way communication) is advisable for the development of the individual in all its areas.

The implementation of interactive learning requires serious preparedness from both the teacher and the students. The application of methods should be gradual, dosed and necessarily methodologically justified. The teacher and students need to

get used to them and gain some experience in using them in their own development. It is obvious that the organization and conduct of classes in an interactive mode should be mutually interesting for both the teacher and the children. It is appropriate to conduct a targeted organizational and methodological lesson with students on the joint development of the "Rules of Cooperation", on which to build a system of attitude, motivation of children for conscientious preparation for interactive lessons. Meanwhile, the use of interactive methods should not be an end in itself for the teacher, so simple interactive methods are recommended first - work in pairs, small groups, brainstorming, etc. It is an effective means of achieving a classroom atmosphere that is most conducive to understanding the ideas, values and spirit of law and civil society as a result of fruitful cooperation and mutual understanding.

Discussion

For discussion, let's consider the logic of pedagogical activity, which ensures the productivity of the implementation of interactive learning in social studies lessons in grades 8-11. Approximate stages of interactive work:

- I. The stage of preparing the teacher and students for interactive learning;
- II. Stage of acquisition of groups;
- III. Stage of educational activity of students in a group;
- IV. Group decision presentation stage;
- V. Stage of examination (at the discretion of the teacher);
- VI. The stage of reflection of the past lesson [6].

Preparation for a lesson based on interactive learning should begin with the formulation of the topic of the lesson, which must certainly contain a problem, a field of contradiction, otherwise the condition for the collision of different points of view, versions will not be provided.

The problematization of the topic should involve, aim students at comparison, comparison, grouping, generalization, analysis and proof (the main elements of problem-based learning).

When planning the organization of interactive work, then it is imperative to change the learning space due to the appropriate convenient placement of school furniture in the office. The next step is the formation of groups of students for interactive work. Generally, two main approaches are used:

- a) division into pairs and triplets (dyads and triads);
- b) role distribution in groups of 4-5 people (for example, a speaker, understanding, constructive critic, organizer, etc.).

Groups in the lesson can be formed at the request of students (free acquisition) or organized by the teacher.

Options for free grouping:

- The teacher names the quantitative composition of the groups (for example, 3 people each), which should be formed in 2-3 minutes.
- Upon entering the classroom, students take cards of different colors or shapes and form appropriate groups.
- The teacher offers students to choose from a list of cards united by a single theme (for example, considering a specific issue from the standpoint of history, foreign experience, various categories of the country's population). The task involves competition in the formation of groups.

Techniques for the formation of groups by the teacher:

- The teacher preliminarily lays out on the tables cards with the names and surnames of the students who should form this microgroup.
- At the entrance to the classroom, the teacher distributes colored cards to students, which is a pass to a certain table, marked with a specific color card.
- It is proposed to choose a table with a letter (A, B, C, ...), indicating the complexity of the task.

It is proposed at the entrance to the class to group according to the principle of commonality of the month of birth.

- It is suggested at the entrance to the class to group according to the first letter of the name.

When completing groups, the pros and cons of each of its two types should be taken into account. In the first case of group formation, when the interests of the schoolchildren themselves are taken into account, the advantages are obvious: an atmosphere conducive to communication is created, which liberates partners, in most cases the children know their capabilities, and the “sense of elbow” is strengthened. For the first lessons of interactive learning, this is the most effective method of forming groups. However, it has significant "cons". Groups are formed unequal quantitatively and qualitatively, which entails the corresponding results of their joint activities. It is possible that the interest of communication may prevail over the need to complete the task. Outside these groups, there may be students who do not have a relationship with the class. In such a situation, this will contribute to the further destruction of relations in the class.

The formation of groups can be complicated by the fact that insecure students may refuse to move from their usual group to another. When planning, this situation should be foreseen, but it is necessary to plan the work of groups with a shift composition. Gradually, the cognitive and social motivation of such students will increase [6].

Conclusions

In mutual learning, each group studies its questions, then sends its representatives to other groups. The consultant succinctly and briefly states the essence of the issue, requires writing down the main key provisions in a notebook, and, if necessary, pronounces these provisions with the students. In turn, replacing each other, consultants from different groups explain all the questions. The abstract of the new material is gradually filled with information. At the end of the lesson, the teacher evaluates the abstract, checks the students' knowledge. The abstract is jointly corrected, inaccuracies in it are eliminated. However, work to eliminate errors and

inaccuracies identified in the lesson can also be done at home. Interactive learning, as well as any type of modern learning, requires a mandatory stage of reflection, when it is discussed what is clear for students, not difficult to learn, and what causes difficulties. Self-analysis, exchange of opinions, evaluation of the results of interaction are also important here. To prevent the repetition of negative assessments, attitudes (this is inevitable) on the part of individual students, the teacher should systematically analyze the employment and emotional state of these children.

In the process of group work, intensive socialization of students occurs, interacting, they gain experience in communication and cooperation in its various manifestations, master the skills and abilities of independent cognitive activity, assimilate stereotypes of partner behavior based on a set of values of equality, honesty, freedom, responsibility, purposefulness, humanity, respect for the rights of another person, justice, mutual assistance and participation. In the traditional system of education, where the frontal method of education prevails, of course, socialization occurs more weakly, since the act of learning is carried out in relation to the entire class team.

In the pedagogical literature, the concept of "group work" has three different meanings. The traditional (first) meaning under group lessons considers fragments of lessons when students work in small groups. The second meaning is an occupation within the framework of a group organizational form of learning, when the speaker addresses the text to several people [1]. The third value of group lessons is a unit of the group way of teaching in class-lesson and lecture-seminar systems [5].

The typology of the concepts of general and specific forms of organization of education was introduced by V.K. Dyachenko. The typology is based on possible structures of human interaction [1]:

- mediated communication of people corresponds to an individually mediated form of learning;

- interaction in pairs of constant composition - steam room;
- communication of people in a group, when the speaker sends the text to several listeners at the same time - group;
- the interaction of people, when communication takes place in pairs of shifts - collective.

The main feature of group forms of classes is the commonality of the learning situation, when all students in the class perform the same task for a certain period of time, in the same way and by the same means. The second sign of group lessons is the same route for mastering the curriculum, which implies the unity of the sequence of studying sections, topics of educational material [4].

The following features are characteristic of collective forms of organizing training sessions:

- there is no common learning situation: children learn for different purposes, learn different content in different ways and means, for different times;
- different students master the same educational material by different routes;
- the presence of consolidated groups, as a space of intersection of different educational routes of students.

It should also be emphasized that in the educational process there are several consolidated groups that differ in the topic under study and organization.

Thus, the collective way of organizing classes is more in line with the tasks of interactivity of students' activities.

In conclusion, it should be noted that independent interactive learning of students cannot be left to chance, while operating with the freedom of educational activity. Purposeful joint diverse work of the teacher and students in the process of mastering new material should be carried out. Interactive methods create a favorable environment for the purposeful development of personal qualities and learning activities of students based on analysis, generalization, reflection and mutual

influence. The potential of interactive methods is realized in conditions of mutual understanding, partnership and awareness of the unity of purpose.

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